

Table 1: *Friedman* test results

Algorithm	K	Groups
Euclídiana	6	a
Manhatthan	6	a
Coseno	6	a
Jaccard	6	a
Cosseno	7	ab
Jaccard	7	ab
Coseno	5	abc
Jaccard	5	abc
Chebyshev	6	abc
Euclidiano	8	abcd
Manhattan	8	abcd
Coseno	3	abcde
Euclidiano	3	abcde
Chebyshev	9	abcdef